

GENDER MAINSTREAMING IN GOVERNANCE: MODEL AND POLICY

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Abstract. Gender inequality is a condition that places women after men which then raises the gender equality movement through Gender Mainstreaming (PUG). Gender mainstreaming has not been too revealing of results and enjoyed equally in Lampung Province so that a policy is needed as a real effort in implementing Gender Mainstreaming. This study aims to look at the efforts of the Lampung Province government as policy makers in realizing gender equality in Lampung Province through a qualitative approach. The results of this study indicate that Gender Mainstreaming in Lampung Province is stated in the Lampung Provincial Regulation Number 10 of 2011 concerning Gender Mainstreaming in Regional Development and is at the socialization stage as a form of strengthening the acceleration of the implementation of Gender Mainstreaming in Lampung Province.

Keywords: Policy, Gender Equality, and Gender Mainstreaming

INTRODUCTION

Women have been regarded as a minority whose position is number two after men, this condition called gender inequality. In the end of 19th until 20th century, the history of women's movements in Indonesia is began in the era of R.A. Kartini, and continue voiced in various forms until now, which focus on woman protection tried to get equal rights and position with men. Gender equality is affirmed in the CEDAW Convention which bases three main principles, namely the principle of substantive equality, the principle of non-discrimination, and the principle of state obligations. Nationally, the existence of Gender Mainstreaming (*Pengarusutamaan Gender - PUG*) in Presidential Instruction Number 9 of 2000 which explains that PUG is a strategy to achieve gender equality and justice through policies and programs that pay attention to the experiences, aspirations, needs, and problems of women and men into the process of planning, implementing, monitoring and evaluating all policies and programs in various fields of life and the development sector. Gender mainstreaming guarantees that development provides access, participation, control and benefits for women and men in various planned activities including legislation, policies or programs in all midwives and levels. Access means that both women and men, including marginalized groups, have equal access to development resources. Participation means that every citizen, both women and men, including disabled, can play an active role in development, they are not just objects but also subjects.

Control means that all levels of society can participate in speaking out their contents to participate in the decision-making process. While the benefits mean that the development results are felt to benefit all citizens, both women and men, including *diffable*.¹ . In order for gender equality and justice manifest, a policy is needed based on the needs and experiences of the gap between women and men in Indonesia.

The Indonesia governance effort to prevent, handle and resolve the problem of violence against women are visible such as in Lampung Province, while the effort on gender mainstreaming has not been too visible and can be enjoyed equally. In order to realize gender equality and justice in Lampung Province, a policy is needed as a real effort. This policy was then poured into Provincial Regulation No. 10 of 2011 concerning Gender Mainstreaming in Regional Development. After the regional regulation was passed, the next obstacle is that not all Regional Government Department or *Organisasi Perangkat Daerah (OPD)* in Lampung Province have implemented it, at least around 20 *OPDs* have implemented it. The reason is that not all implementers in each Regional Government understand Gender Mainstreaming, so that each *OPD* has not shown a significant contribution in the implementation of Gender Mainstreaming as stipulated in the regional regulation². While in the idea of a political-administrative dichotomy, the most authoritative institution to implement a policy is the executive or the government³. These constraints must certainly be responded by the government as policy makers. This was stated by Anderson in Hamidi (2016; 36), who said that one of the implications of the policy concept made by the government was a response to the need for a policy regarding certain matters. As a reflection of the concept in terms of Gender Mainstreaming, the government needs strengthening in accelerating Gender Mainstreaming in Lampung Province.⁴

RESEARCH METHOD

This study aims to provide a description and analysis of the Gender Mainstreaming policy model implemented in Lampung Province which is displayed through narrative texts. This description and analysis is obtained through a qualitative approach, in accordance with what Bogdan and Taylor conveyed in Sujarweni, that qualitative research is one of the research procedures that produces descriptive data in the form of speech or writing and the behavior of the people

¹ The Ministry of Women's Empowerment and Child Protection. Manual book of Gender Mainstreaming or *Pengarusutamaan Gender (PUG)* for Local Government. (Jakarta : The Ministry of Women's Empowerment and Child Protection, 2016), Page 17.

² Interview with Secretary II *Focal Point PUG* Lampung Province Periode 2017-2019 on September 2018

³ Erwan Agus Purwanto dan Dyah Ratih Sulistyastuti, *Implementasi Kebijakan Publik: Konsep dan Aplikasinya di Indonesia*. (Yogyakarta: Gava Media, 2015), Page. 125.

⁴ Muchlis Hamidi. *Kebijakan Publik: Proses, Analisis dan Partisipasi*. (Bogor: Ghalia Indonesia, 2015), Page 36.

observed⁵. Data collection was carried out through interviews with Secretary II of Focal Point PUG in Lampung Province, which aimed to determine the Gender Mainstreaming policy model from the implementation. Data collection is also done by documentation as secondary data. The document in this study is in the form of Lampung Province Regional Regulation Number 10 of 2011 concerning Gender Mainstreaming in Regional Development, reports on Gender Mainstreaming Training Activities, Lampung Governor's Decree on Working Groups and Gender Mainstreaming Focal Points, and Provincial Medium-Term Development Plans (RPJMD) Lampung in 2015-2019. Interviews and documentation on this research were carried out directly at the Women's Empowerment Service and Child Protection of Lampung Province as OPDs and the main movers that overshadow the issue of inequality and gender injustice.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Anderson in Hamidi said that public policy is a policy made by government institutions or officials. Furthermore Anderson mentioned five implications of the concept, namely public policy is a goal-oriented action, public policy contains a series of actions taken all the time, public policy is a response to the need for a policy regarding certain things, public policy is a picture of activities the government is actually and not just a desire to be implemented, and government policy can be an active or passive activity in dealing with a problem⁶. The concept of the policy is in accordance with the gender mainstreaming policy in regional development as a government effort in realizing gender equality and equality.

Gender Mainstreaming in Lampung Province as Goal-Oriented Action

Gender Mainstreaming is a strategy of integrating gender perspectives in development in order to realize gender equality. Whereas women's empowerment is an effort to increase women's capacity and quality⁷. Lampung Province reflects the mandate contained in Presidential Instruction Number 9 of 2000 concerning Gender Mainstreaming in Development with Lampung Province Regional Regulation Number 10 of 2011 concerning Gender Mainstreaming in Regional Development. So that in formulating policies, programs, and activities, each agency must make it as a basis, in accordance with the regional regulations which explain that gender mainstreaming in the area aims to provide direction for the local government and DPRD Lampung Province in the formulation of gender integration strategies through planning up to evaluation of policies, programs and

⁵ V. Wiratna Sujarweni, *Metodologi Penelitian*, (Yogyakarta : PT Pustaka Baru, 2014), Page. 6.

⁶ Hamidi, *Op Cit.*

⁷ Training Materials for the Acceleration of PUG Implementation Strategy in the Lampung Province PPPA Service Activity Report of 2017

development activities in all sectors. In the regional regulation, it was explained that the formulation of policies, programs and development activities using a gender perspective was carried out using the Gender Analysis Workflow (GAW) method or other analytical methods. The GAW model is an analysis model to find out gender gaps with four aspects, namely access, participation, control, and benefits obtained by men and women in development programs / activities ranging from policy planning to monitoring⁸.

Gender Mainstreaming Policy Is a Response to the Need for a Policy Regarding Certain Things

Gender mainstreaming is a policy that accommodates problems, needs, aspirations, and experiences between women and men. Lampung Province has more male population than women with a ratio of 105.16 which means the opportunity for gender inequality is quite large. Gender issues are a strategic issue that is of concern in the preparation of the Lampung Province RPJMD for 2015-2019, including the Lampung Province GPA of 63.50% or in number 9 on Sumatra Island, IDG Lampung Province at 65.86% or number sequence 4 on Sumatra Island, and still vulnerable to trafficking problems for women. The male and female Labor Participation Rates (LBR) in Lampung Province in 2016 showed a considerable difference, namely male LBRs of 86.18% while women were 52.17%. In addition, the female unemployment rate reached 4.86% while the male unemployment rate was 4.48%. Women's participation in the Lampung Province DPRD in 2016 has not reached 30%, namely women legislative members only number 12 while men number 73. The third mission of Lampung Province is to improve the quality of education, health, science and technology, community culture, and religious tolerance aimed at improving the quality of gender equality development and family welfare with the aim of increasing the development index and gender equality through the implementation of gender mainstreaming strategies in policy making, planning, and budgeting, with the policy direction of implementing Gender Responsive Budgeting (GRB). It can be concluded that PUG is an integrated policy as a form of response that accommodates all gender-related problems in Lampung Province. The application of GRB as a further step in the Gender Mainstreaming policy. But the reality is that not all Regional Government Department that implement GRBs, because of human resources or in other words the implementers do not understand gender and the frequent transfer of implementers to date is still an obstacle in the implementation of Gender Mainstreaming policies in Lampung Province, so that implementers of Gender Mainstreaming socialization and training were replaced with new implementers who do not necessarily understand gender

⁸ *Ibid.*

mainstreaming, so that understanding is given from the beginning. This is what makes the implementation of gender mainstreaming acceleration policy in Lampung Province hampered.

Gender Mainstreaming Policy is an Overview of Government Activities Actually and Not Just a Wish That Will Be Implemented

Lampung Province Regional Regulation Number 10 of 2011 concerning Gender Mainstreaming in Regional Development is clear evidence that Lampung Province implements the mandate contained in Presidential Instruction Number 9 of 2000 concerning PUG in Development. The regional regulation contains instructions for establishing a working group and gender mainstreaming focal point as an effort to accelerate gender mainstreaming in Lampung Province. The gender mainstreaming working group is a forum for consultation for implementers and activists of gender mainstreaming from various agencies or institutions in Lampung Province. The working group functions as the coordinator of the development of ideas and thoughts of the focal points in their respective Regional Government Departments in the decision making process, especially in planning policies and gender issues that develop in their environment, as a forum for communicating meetings with decision makers in each Regional Government department or institutions in gender mainstreaming meetings and discussions, as well as implementing women empowerment programs in the regional department Work Plan and RPJM agencies or section heads assigned to handle women's empowerment as working group secretaries. Based on Lampung Governor's Decree Number G / 294 / V.08 / HK / 2017 Concerning Amendments to Attachment of Lampung Governor's Decree Number G / 259 / II.12 / HK / 2015 Concerning Formation of gender mainstreaming Working Groups, Governor and Deputy Governor of Lampung act as advisors, Secretary The Province of Lampung acted as the director, the Head of the Lampung Provincial Development Planning Agency acted as the chairman, and the Head of the PPPA Office of Lampung Province as the Regional department responsible for women's empowerment became the gender mainstreaming working group secretary. Members of the PUG working group consist of the heads of each Regional department and heads of agencies related to the Lampung Provincial Government, including; Dr. H. Abdul Moeloek Lampung Province, Lampung Provincial Hospital, Lampung Province Inspector, and others.

The members of the gender mainstreaming working group come from every sector that supports development in Lampung Province, this means that gender mainstreaming in Lampung Province is not only the responsibility of the Regional department that deals with women's issues, but is the responsibility of each Regional Department and agency in Lampung Province. Meanwhile Gender

mainstreaming Focal Points are regional department apparatuses who have the ability to carry out gender mainstreaming in their respective work units. Gender mainstreaming Focal Points have a very important role as the main executor of this policy. Gender Mainstreaming Focal Points are formed at the provincial and district or city scale, whose tasks include:

- 1) Promoting Gender mainstreaming in work units
- 2) Facilitate the preparation of a Regional Government Department Work Plan that has a Gender perspective
- 3) Conduct training, socialization and Gender Mainstreaming advocacy to all officials and staff within each Regional Government Department
- 4) Report the implementation of Gender to the respective Regional Government Department leaders
- 5) Encourage the implementation of gender analysis of policies, programs and activities in work units
- 6) Facilitating the preparation of gender profiles for each Regional Government Department

Based on Lampung Governor's Decree Number G / 295 / V.08 / HK / 2017 Concerning Amendments to Annex Governor Decree Number G / 310 / II.12 / 2015 concerning Establishment of Lampung Province gender mainstreaming Focal Points Year 2015-2019, Gender mainstreaming Focal Point Coordinator is the Head of the Field Government Planning and Human Development Regional Development Planning Agency of Lampung Province, one secretary is responsible for the Head of the Division of Quality of Life for Women and Family Quality of PPPA Lampung Province, and the second secretary is the Head of gender mainstreaming Section for Social, Political, and Legal Services of the Provincial PPPA Lampung. While those who are members are the heads of fields or heads of the sub-division of planning and administration for each Regional government department in Lampung Province. With the establishment of the Lampung Province Gender Mainstreaming working group and focal point, the second step of the Gender mainstreaming policy in Lampung province has been carried out.

Gender Mainstreaming as a Policy in Overcoming Gender Inequality

In the Lampung Provincial Regulation Number 10 of 2011 concerning PUG in Regional Development, it is said that PUG in regional development is based on respect for human rights, so it needs to be supported by every sector through programs and activities made by the DPO and agencies within the government. In this case the bottom line is human resources as the subject of policy. Goggin et al. in Purwanto and Sulistyastuti said that commitment and competence are two

important requirements that must be possessed by personnel who are mandated to achieve policy objectives in implementation. The obstacle in the implementation of PUG in Lampung Province is that not a few DPOs do not understand PUG so that PUG cannot be implemented. These constraints were conveyed at each OPD meeting with the working group and PUG focal point. The solution to this obstacle is the socialization and training given to each PUG driver representing the OPD.

This socialization and training aims to provide the mobilizing agency with the ability to carry out gender analysis in regional planning and budgeting. The material presented at the activity was about gender analysis and the steps. First, choose policies, programs and activities with a gender perspective. The next step is to see whether there are gender gaps through gender disaggregated data, raising gender issues in planning by paying attention to access, participation, control, and benefits, and recognizing gender issues in internal and external institutions or organizational cultures that cause gender issues. The next step is reformulating policies and developing a gender-responsive action plan, establishing the basis for measuring the progress of implementation by looking at whether the gender gap has diminished or no longer exists and whether there are changes in behavior and values of policy planners, programs, and activities both internally and externally OPD . Other material regarding Gender Responsive Planning and Budgeting (PPRG), starting from the basis, reasons, stages, and how to compile the PPRG through the Gender Budget Statement (GBS), is a document that states the existence of gender equality and justice in planning and budgeting activities. The training also conveyed about institutions in PUG along with their duties and functions. The institutions include Working Groups, Technical Teams, Focal Points, Driving Teams, and the PPRG Joint Secretariat.⁹

The training is not only the delivery of material but also the simulation. The training presenters are people who are experts and understand PUG, so the training can be effective and efficient. The training was an effort to improve human resources in the OPD as a driving force for gender mainstreaming.

CONCLUSION

Gender Mainstreaming Policy in Lampung Province is stated in the form of Lampung Province Regional Regulation Number 10 of 2011 concerning PUG in Regional Development. Based on these regional regulations, Gender mainstreaming aims to improve the role and independence of institutions that handle women's empowerment. Gender mainstreaming in Lampung Province is still at the stage of socialization and training as a step to strengthen the acceleration of gender mainstreaming implementation. Gender Mainstreaming working groups and focal

⁹ Laporan Kegiatan Dinas PPPA Provinsi Lampung Tahun 2017, *Op. Cit.*

points continue to carry out their duties starting from promoting gender mainstreaming, implementing gender mainstreaming socialization and advocacy in the Regional Government Organization environment and to district or city governments, to encourage the realization of a gender perspective budget. These tasks were carried out in the form of regular training and meetings held to evaluate gender mainstreaming in Lampung Province. The Lampung Provincial Government has carried out its duties as an institution that is synonymous with policies to solve problems.

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